

Synthesis and characterization of oxovanadium(IV) complexes incorporating novel tridentate OOO donor ligands

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Abstract : VOSO₄ reacts with equivalent amount of 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)butane-1,3-dione (H₂L¹) and 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-propane-1,3-dione (H₂L²) in presence of two equivalent sodium acetate in 50% (v/v) aqueous-methanolic medium to afford the brown complexes [V^{IV}O(L¹)(H₂O)]_n (1) and [V^{IV}O(L²)(H₂O)]_n (2) respectively. IR spectra and solubility of complexes in common organic solvent along with the geometry of the ligands indicated the polymeric nature of the complexes. Complexes are one-electron paramagnetic and are EPR active displaying axial EPR spectra in DMSO solution at 77 K. They exhibit three transitions in the visible region at ~660 nm, ~590 nm and ~430 nm due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} ; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ respectively.

Keywords : Oxovanadium(IV) complexes, electronic spectra, EPR spectra.

Introduction

Vanadium in its +IV and +V oxidation state has strong affinity towards O/N donor ligands due to their hard acidic nature¹⁻⁵. 1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)but-1,3-dione (H₂L¹) and 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-phenyl-prop-1,3-dione (H₂L²) in their enol form (Scheme 1) are important tridentate diacidic oxygen donor ligands. From the structural features of these ligands, however, it is evident that all the donor sites are not in the same plane. To study the complexing behaviour of these compounds with VO²⁺ ion, this work has been done. Such studies are important because of their chemical and biochemical significance⁶⁻¹⁰.

Scheme 1. Ligands used in this study.

Experimental

Materials :

VOSO₄.5H₂O and sodium acetate trihydrate were obtained from Loba Chemical Company. H₂L¹ and H₂L² were synthesized by the reported methods^{11,12}. Solvents were of analytical reagent grade and used without further purification.

Preparation of the metal complexes [VO(L)(H₂O)]_n (1, 2) :

The complexes were prepared by the same general method. Details are given for one representative case.

[VO(L¹)(H₂O)]_n (1) :

To a warm methanolic solution (20 cm³) of H₂L¹ (0.178 g, 1 mmol) and sodium acetate trihydrate (0.272 g, 2 mmol) was added aqueous solution (10 cm³) of VOSO₄.5H₂O (0.253 g, 1 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at ~60 °C. A brown compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with water, aqueous-methanol and then dried over silica gel (fused). Yield : 0.235 g (90%). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₀O₅V : C, 45.98; H, 3.83. Found : C, 45.78; H, 3.88%; λ_{max} (DMSO)/nm : 650 (22), 585 (29), 430 (745).

$[VO(L^2)(H_2O)]_n$ (**2**) :

Yield : 0.30 g (93%). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{12}O_5V$: C, 55.73; H, 3.72. Found : C, 55.61; H, 3.82%; λ_{max} (CH_2Cl_2)/nm : 660 (21), 590 (27), 435 (730).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O analyzer. Electronic spectra (in DMSO or in CH_2Cl_2) were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (as KBr pellets) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. The EPR spectra (X-band) in DMSO solution were recorded on a E-112 Century series Varian E-102 Microwave bridge spectrometer. Tetracyanoethane (tcne) ($g = 2.0027$) was used to calibrate the EPR spectra.

Results and discussion

Reaction of $VOSO_4$ with equimolar amount of H_2L^1 or H_2L^2 (general abbreviation, H_2L) in presence of two equivalent CH_3COONa afforded the brown complexes $[V^{IV}O(L^1)(H_2O)]_n$ (**1**) and $[V^{IV}O(L^2)(H_2O)]_n$ (**2**) respectively in excellent yield. The reaction can be represented as :

Complexes are not appreciably soluble in common organic solvents viz. CH_3OH , CH_2Cl_2 , CH_3CN indicating their polymeric nature.

IR spectra of the complexes :

Selected IR spectra of the complexes which are relevant for their characterization are collected in Table 1. Complexes display a strong band near 1000 cm^{-1} , as-

Table 1. Selective IR (in KBr disc) data (cm^{-1}) of the complexes **1** and **2**

Complexes	V=O	C-O _{enolic}	C-O _{enolic}	C=O
$[VO(L^1)(H_2O)]_n$ (1)	998	1219	1374	1630
$[VO(L^2)(H_2O)]_n$ (2)	1001	1240	1382	1620

Table 2. Magnetic moment (at room temperature) and EPR spectral data^a [in DMSO at 77 K] of the complexes **1** and **2**

Complexes	μ_{eff} (BM)	g_{\parallel} ($10^4 A_{\parallel}/\text{cm}^{-1}$)	g_{\perp} ($10^4 A_{\perp}/\text{cm}^{-1}$)	$10^4 A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}}$
$[VO(L^1)(H_2O)]_n$ (1)	1.71	1.934 (170.1)	1.972 (70.2)	168.3
$[VO(L^2)(H_2O)]_n$ (2)	1.73	1.933 (171.2)	1.974 (69.7)	168.3

^aLimit of error in g values : 0.003 and A values : $3 \times 10^4\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

signed to V=O stretch indicating the penta-coordinated environment around the vanadium¹³⁻¹⁸. A medium intensity band near 3135 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of coordinated H_2O molecule¹³. The $\nu_{C=O}$ of the free ligands observed near 1680 cm^{-1} is reduced to $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes suggesting its involvement in bonding.

Magnetic moment and EPR spectra of the complexes :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \sim 1.73\text{ BM}$, Table 2) indicating tetravalent state of the vanadium.

Complexes are EPR-active displaying axial EPR spectra (in frozen dimethylsulfoxide, 77 K) with well resolved ^{51}V ($I = 7/2$) hyperfine lines. Parameters are collected in Table 2 and representative spectra are displayed in Fig. 1. The $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ and $A_{\parallel} \gg A_{\perp}$ relationships are characteristic of an axially compressed d_{xy} configuration¹⁹⁻²². The experimental A_{\parallel} values (Table 2) are close to the estimated A_{\parallel} ($A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}}$) values obtained by using the additivity relationship presented by Chasteen²³.

On the basis of IR and EPR spectra of the complexes as well as their solubility in common organic solvents, a gross structure of the complexes, may be represented as in Scheme 2.

Electronic spectra of the complexes :

The brown tetravalent complexes **1** and **2** display three ligand-field transitions in the visible region (mentioned in

Fig. 1. X-band EPR spectra of **1** in DMSO solution at 77 K.

Note

Scheme 2. Probable gross structure of the complexes.

the Experimental part) near 660, 590 and 430 nm, due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} ; $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions²⁴ respectively.

Conclusion

This study indicates that, though these ligands (H_2L^{1-2}) contain three donor sites but because of the stereochemistry, they can not bind the same metal with three coordinating sites. They function as a bidentate and a monodentate ligand and due to this reason; the complexes with vanadium are polymeric in nature. Magnetic susceptibility measurements and EPR spectra indicates that the tetravalent complexes formed by these ligands are magnetically dilute.

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References

1. D. Patra, N. Biswas, B. Mondal, M. G. B. Drew and T. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2012, **48**, 264.
2. B. Mondal, M. G. B. Drew and T. Ghosh, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 2296.

3. B. Mondal, M. G. B. Drew and T. Ghosh, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **362**, 3303.
4. B. Mondal, M. G. B. Drew, R. Banerjee and T. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 3197.
5. B. Mondal, T. Ghosh, M. Sutradhar, G. Mukherjee, M. G. B. Drew and T. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2008, **27**, 2193.
6. J. M. Arber, E. de Boer, C. D. Garner, S. S. Hasnain and R. Wever, *Biochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 7968.
7. R. Wever and K. Kustin, *Adv. Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **35**, 81.
8. A. Butler and C. J. Carrano, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **109**, 61.
9. D. Rehder, *Angew. Chem., Int. Edn. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 148.
10. H. Vitler and D. Rehder, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **136**, L7.
11. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1381.
12. T. S. Wheeler, *Org. Synth. Coll. Vol.*, 1963, **4**, 478.
13. L. J. Theriot, G. O. Carlisle and H. J. Hu, *J. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2841.
14. A. P. Ginsberg, E. Koubek and H. J. Williams, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1656.
15. A. Syamal and K. S. Kale, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 225.
16. A. Syamal and K. S. Kale, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 992.
17. S. Bhattacharya and T. Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 601.
18. S. Bhattacharya and T. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **76**, 373.
19. J. Chakravarty, S. Dutta, A. Dey and A. Chakravorty, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1994, 557.
20. G. R. Hausen, T. A. Kabanos, A. D. Keramidias, D. Mentzafos and A. Terzis, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2587.
21. T. Ghosh, S. Bhattacharya, A. Das, G. Mukherjee and M. G. B. Drew, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **358**, 989.
22. D. Patra, N. Biswas, B. Mondal, M. G. B. Drew and T. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2012, **48**, 264.
23. N. D. Chasteen, "Biological Magnetic Resonance", eds. J. Lawrence, L. J. Berliner and J. Reuben, Plenum, New York, 1981, Vol. 3, p. 53.
24. C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.

